

REVISITING THE PERFORMANCE TASKS OF SECONDARY STUDENTS: TALES OF TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD TEACHERS

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Abstract. This study explored the performance tasks of secondary students in Technology and Livelihood Education as narrated by the teachers. There were eight (8) TLE teachers who participated in the study coming from Kapalong East District, Davao del Norte. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas of the teacher participants. The in-depth-interview was employed to gather some information as regards to their respective experiences. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged as pertains to the experiences of the participants: : the experiences of the TLE teachers revealed three themes such as: Increased self- esteem, Heightened motivation and Low student involvement. The coping mechanisms of the teachers were Encouraging full activity participation, strengthening class teamwork and inspiring actual class demonstration. The educational management insights were focused on two factors: Keeping track on students' skills and Creating group circles. For the principals or school heads to be more sensitive to the needs of the teachers and the students. The curricular offering in TLE classes were more complex as compared to other courses in the curriculum. The TLE teachers may be more observant on their actions and classwork activities. They may look into the individual needs of their students. The teachers may also acknowledge the students' performances and help the students who are not inclined to the area of home economics.

KEY WORDS

1. performance tasks 2. tales of technology 3. livelihood teachers

1. Introduction

The teaching of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) has become more open to new and modern approaches. Unlike in the past years where there were limited resources. This academic discipline is no longer specific to cooking and household management, it opened its doors to a more complicated and integrated discipline. Further, the students' performance in terms of their skills and knowledge learned in the course were assessed according to the student's capacity. Developing countries such as the Asian Region, it is challenging both for teachers and the students because of the adaptation and development of the latest software, hardware, and electronic communications. In most parts of Asia, most countries are undergoing social and economic changes such as globalization, technology, and industrialization. Even before the pandemic, governments are giving high priority to Online Distance Learning (Gao)

and Hutagalung, 2020). According to Tan and Chen (2021), there is a massive challenge in replicating collaborative classroom learning in the online classroom. Students cannot fully collaborate online; there is only a two-way communication mechanism for both teachers and students; limited physical demonstrations of science activities and experiments; and creates additional affordance of students' engagement within the virtual classroom. Petalla, M. B., Doromal, A. C. (2021) revealed that providing relevant learning activities in a responsive classroom is necessary to develop 21st-century skills and competencies among students. That is why performance task assessment comes in as part of the educational reform brought about by the K to 12 Curriculum of the Department of Education. Further, they articulated that result of the study revealed that planning of tasks, execution of tasks, and consequences of tasks were contributory to the challenges encountered by students. Challenges on the planning of tasks included quality of leadership, preparation, and articulation. The absence of skills and lack of supervision and motivation were included in the challenges specific to the execution of tasks. Consequences of tasks included challenges brought about by unreliable scores received and the limited learning gained. Casingal (2022) postulated that teachers either do not explain the content of the rubrics or do not present them at all when assigning online performance tasks. Teachers should be familiar with the process of developing rubrics. They should understand how to set appropriate activities based on the pupils' degree of comprehension. In addition, most Filipino elementary pupils find giving simultaneous performance tasks difficult. They cannot do their studies because they lack the necessary equipment and slow internet connection. In the local scenario, specifically in Kapa-long East District, Davao del Norte, I noticed that some of the teachers have been engrossed in making assessments of the performance tasks of their students in technology and livelihood education. Most of the TLE teachers as I have observed had experienced difficulties in dealing with their students in the secondary level, they also encountered problems in developing the skills of the students, these may be due to some other reasons not yet known since we just returned to the face to face classes.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore the experiences of technology and livelihood education teachers in assessing the performance tasks of their students. This research also dealt with the coping mechanisms of the TLE teachers who were teaching in the secondary level. Their insights about their respective experiences in their classes were also determined.

- (1) What are the experiences of TLE teachers as they reckon the performance tasks of the students?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of teachers on their struggles in teaching TLE among secondary students?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

1.2. Synthesis—The readings and significant literatures and studies presented in this research were aligned with the intentions of this study to explore the experiences of technology and livelihood education teachers in their ways of assessing the performance tasks of the students in the secondary level. The discussions and thorough explanations of the experts in TLE cited herein were substantial and were able to discuss the significance of the study of the various disciplines of home economics.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of The Study

1.3. *Theory*—This study was founded on the Backward design or Understanding by Design is a systematic, planned curriculum design model developed by Wiggins and McTighe (1998). The theory of this model encapsulates the assumption that 'students understand knowledge and skills, and then apply what they understand in a different context'. This model consists of three basic components; defining the desired outcomes, determining the evaluation evidence, and planning the teaching. The determination of the performance tasks and evidence by which the students transfer what they have learned takes place before the planning of the instruction . This study was further instituted on the proposition of Kim (2005) who claimed that performance tasks improve student learn-

ing in general and positively impact the learners' learning attitudes. In addition, teachers can determine the effectiveness of the learning process and mastery of the lesson through the results and outputs of the tasks. Unaccomplished performance tasks indicate unsuccessful performance due to a lot of factors. One factor to consider is its non-conformity to the assessment tool. Another is the attainment of the mastery of the lesson. Unaccomplished performance task indicates students' inability to develop a deeper understanding of the lesson. It also impedes the progression of the lesson and prohibits the teacher from measuring accurate knowledge of the students. It has also been tested and observed that many students fail to accomplish the required performance task because of their unidentified problems

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration.

This chapter discusses the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration. The three most common

qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally

occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research – undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model for example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defend a research paradigms a "basic set of belief that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012) reality is a subjective and multiple as

seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the actualities on the experiences of TLE teachers were dichotomized to provide a better interpretation about the problems of the teachers in assessing the performance tasks of the students. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I will identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief". The purpose of this research was to gather significant particulars on the experiences of the TLE teachers from their schools particularly those coming from Kapalong East District, Davao del Norte. I assured to establish a close interaction with

the participants to gain direct information that will shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on the encounters of the TLE teachers who were conducting the students performance tasks in their schools. Axiology refers to role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I therefore preserve the merit of the participant's answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant's personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in explaining the experiences of the teachers as they performed their responsibilities in assessing the students performance tasks. As a researcher, I agree with the post modernism philosophy of Afzal-os-sadat Hossieni (2011). I believe that the aims of education are teaching critical thinking, production of knowledge, development of individual and social identity, self-creation. In postmodern education teachers just lead students to discover new things. They provide opportunities to discuss about different subjects and make creative ways. In this situation student learn to listen to other voices. They tolerate others criticism and try to think in critical way. They learn to respect other cultures and nationalities. Also they emphasize on cooperative learning independent learning, and dialectic, critical and verbal methods. It is deduced that postmodernism and creativity are embedded in each other and we can find the result of this opinion in postmodern education.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study the experiences of the TLE teachers were set free based from their personal narratives particularly those who were implementing the assessment of the performance tasks of the students in their TLE classes. The researcher's drive in knowing the deeper meaning of the predicaments of the TLE teachers became the basis for doing a qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena". By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher predicted that the subjective experiences and coping mechanisms of the TLE teachers were explored and insights were drawn as basis for the possible future researches and

policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process the

2.4. Research Participants—The participants in this study were composed of eight (8) informants. The selected informants were the TLE teachers coming from Kapalong East District, Davao del Norte. All the participants were the technology and livelihood education teachers from various nearby schools. They must have been teaching the course for at least one (1) year. All the participants were coming from the secondary level schools regardless of their age, sex and marital status. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size the quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for

2.5. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data such as interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs

researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation or experiences and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study phenomenology attempts to extract the most pure, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing is used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing (Maxwell, 2013).

most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25 and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

to anticipate issues of data collection, called “field issues,” which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there are seven steps in the process of data collection. First is the site or individual; the participants were the TLE teachers from Kapalong East District, Davao del Norte Second is the access and rapport; letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student

for the approval of the division superintendent; letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal and the concerned elementary teachers were prepared for easy collection of data. The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. There were eight (8) informants selected in this study. The selected teachers were considered group of individuals who can best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered as individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the eight (8) informants. The fifth is the recording procedures; the use of a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the storing of data; Davidson's (1996) suggested the use of database in backing up information collected

2.6. *Data Analysis*—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger

and noting changes for all types of research studies. The COVID 19 Health Protocols. The data was collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (AITF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippines which was convened in January 2020. The Collection of data or the In-Depth Interview (IDI) was conducted following the protocols for Social Distancing which is one of the mandates of AITF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. In this study, the IDI was conducted with utmost care so that social distancing is followed and that at least 2 meters between persons was made. For some participants who missed the face-to-face social distancing efforts, the videocall via messenger, viber, zoom or google meet was used to gather the data or responses of the participants. The participants also filled-in the Interview Form provided to them and submit the same to the researcher.

units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This was called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

that it's a flexible method which can be both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she is are interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources,

which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation. The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned is the use of environmental triangulation best suit the environment of the research being conducted.

Fig. 3. Experiences of TLE teachers as they reckon the performance tasks of the students

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and its answers based on the responses of the participants of the study. The TLE teacher participants exposed their stories as they navigated through their classes. The study also looked into the coping mechanisms of the teachers in their respective classes, their propositions to improve their classes were also considered particularly those teachers in Kapalong East District, Davao del Norte.

3.1. *The experiences of TLE teachers as they reckon the performance tasks of the students.*—

3.1.1. *Increased self-esteem*—The self-esteem of the students played an important role in their learning progress. The greater the self-esteem of the students, the better are their class performances. This means that the more the

students get involved with their class work, the better they learn the skills in the TLE classes.

3.1.2. *Heightened motivation*—As per observation of the teachers, during the interview, they noticed an increase of student’s motivation in their classes. Maybe, this was due to the idea that students were more excited to attend to their classes since the pandemic. They somehow missed the face-to-face classes.

3.1.3. *Low student involvement*—Student involvement is one of the many factors in class work. It is expected that students must do their performance tasks at the highest expected outcomes, however, this is not the case in some of

the students under study. Some of the students did not bother to perform their class tasks as expected. It turned out that only a few of the group members were performing well, other students remained as audience during the conduct of the activities.

3.1.4. *The coping mechanisms of teachers on their struggles in teaching TLE among secondary students*—

3.1.5. *Encouraging full activity participation*—Due to lack of interest among the stu-

dents in TLE classes, there was a need to do something about the student’s reception to their

Fig. 4. Coping mechanisms of teachers on their struggles in teaching TLE among secondary students

class activities. The students may be encouraged to fully participate in their class activities, this means that they can maximize their full potential by performing their class activities.

3.1.6. Strengthening class teamwork—One of the coping mechanisms of the TLE teachers was to strengthen the class team work. The greater the teamwork per group, the better would be their performance. This also means that the closer the students together in their group, the better are outcomes of their activities.

3.1.7. Inspiring actual class demonstration—One of the themes that emerged during the analysis of the responses of the participants of this study was to inspire the students to perform in the class. Class performances are significant activities that develop students life skills. The more the students perform class demonstration, the better are their skills.

3.1.8. Educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study.—

3.1.9. Keeping track on students' skills.—One of the important tasks of the teachers, particularly the TLE teachers is to keep track on the skills development of their students. The teachers should record the progress of the skills of the students at all times.

3.1.10. Creating group circles—Creating a group circle encourages the students to take part in the learning activities at school. Being with the group circle make the students more comfortable and they feel more relaxed in being with the small group of people. They can ask more questions and clarify simple misunderstandings or misconceptions about the task.

Fig. 5. Educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the stories of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers as they narrated those outputs of the performance’s tasks of their respective students specifically in Kapalong East District, Davao del Norte. To achieve the research objectives, I made use of qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell’s (2006) guidelines in which open ended questions for interview were applied to get authentic understanding of the participants experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own experiences or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which was about their experiences as TLE teachers. Based on the results of thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of the TLE teachers revealed three themes such as: Increased self-esteem, Heightened motivation and Low student involvement. The coping mechanisms of the teachers were Encouraging full activity participation, strengthening class teamwork and inspiring actual class demonstration. The educational management insights were focused on two factors: Keeping track on students’ skills and Creating group circles.

4.1. Implications—The experiences of TLE teachers in Kapalong East District, Davao del Norte revealed several facts in terms of their experiences as teachers. The experiences of the teachers in secondary level TLE course revealed three themes. One of which was increased self-esteem. As classroom teachers, they noticed a great amount of increase in the self-esteem of the students during their class activities. The students showed tremendous interest and confidence in their performance tasks. The second theme was on the student’s heightened motivation. The participants observed that the students were highly motivated to do their performance tasks whenever they were told to present their work. The participants of this study noticed that the students eagerly performed their class work with less supervision. They all enjoyed their class activities and rendered them with great performance outcomes in their classes. On the other hand, one sad experience of the teachers was the low student involvement in class work.

Although not all, but it was noteworthy that there were a few who did not bother about the class activities. They did not show interest on the subject matter. Their participation to group and individual activities was very limited. The coping mechanisms of the participants revealed three themes. The first theme was on encouraging full activity participation. Being in the class would mean to participate well with class activities. It was noted that a few of the students were not interested in the subject matter. To deal with this, the teachers opted to personally encourage the students to do their part in the class activities. The second coping mechanism of the teachers was to strengthen class teamwork. It is very important that all the students are involved in all classroom activities. To do this, the teachers made sure that all the students were members of a certain group or team. These teams should have the characteristics of being approachable and a team player. Each member was given their own responsibilities and tasks to perform. The third coping mechanism was inspiring actual class demonstrations. Although

it is not easy to present or give class demonstrations in the class, the students were properly guided as to what to do during class demonstrations. With the help of their groupmates, the student presenter was guided by the group leader. Each member was given a particular work or responsibility. There were two educational management insights drawn from the participants of this study. The first one was keeping track on students' skills. As teachers, they were responsible in tracking the performance skills of their students. They may list down the well-developed skills and the less-developed skills for further enhancement in the future. The second insight gathered from the participants was on creating group circles. The group circles are students assigned together to work out on specific activity. They discussed the procedures, perform the procedure and end up with the expected outcome of the activity. In this group, the students were given the opportunity to ask questions without hesitations since they were familiar with each other.

4.1.1. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. For the principals or school heads to be more sensitive to the needs of the teachers and the students. The curricular offering in TLE classes were more complex as compared to other courses in the curriculum. The school head may give the kind of scholastic support needed by all the stakeholders in the school. The TLE teachers may be more observant on their actions and classwork activities. They may look into the individual needs of their students.

The teachers may also acknowledge the students' performances and help the students who are not inclined to the area of home economics. The students may be directed well through the lessons conducted in the classrooms at a particular schedule. The students are encouraged to participate in class activities and share their ideas for the benefit of the group members. For the future researchers, similar studies may be conducted in other divisions or schools where the Technology and Livelihood Education are very well established. The researchers may consider other aspects of TLE Asa research avenues to improve the life skills of the students.

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